

not constant. The deviation from constancy in case of sucrose + water is maximum and least in case of glucose + water, whereas urea + water is in between the two. The more the deviation, the greater is the ion-solvent interaction¹⁵. So the order of ion-solvent interaction is sucrose + water > urea + water > glucose + water.

The above observations can be explained as follows. Sucrose contains more hydroxy groups than d-glucose and these hydroxy groups present in the compounds participate in the formation of hydrogen bonds with water molecules and hence the water structure breaks. Sucrose, therefore, is a stronger structure breaker than glucose. As regards urea, it can be said that urea is alkaline in water and acts both as a proton donor and acceptor, and hence in the mixture of urea and water, the structure is likely to be broken. Secondly, due to keto-enol tautomerism in solution urea may contain one hydroxy group which participates in the formation of hydrogen bond with water molecules and structure breaking is observed.

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Synthesis of Some 5-Arylazopyrimidine Derivatives

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IN continuation of our work on the synthesis of 5-arylazopyrimidine derivatives of biological interest¹, we report here the synthesis of three

more series of compounds, namely 2-amino-5-arylo-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidines (I), 5-arylo-2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylpyrimidines (II) and 5-arylo-4,6-dimethyl-2-hydroxypyrimidines (III).

All the compounds (I, II and III) were synthesized in excellent yields by the reaction of different aryldiazonium chlorides with appropriately substituted pyrimidine derivatives. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by their elemental analysis and ir spectra (bands in the region 1630-1590 cm⁻¹ due to -N=N-stretching). The arylazo group at position-5 was further confirmed by reducing three arylazo derivatives (one from each series) with Zn and AcOH. 2-Amino-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-5-phenylazopyrimidine (I, X=Y=H), on reduction, afforded 2,5-diamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine while II (X=Y=H) and III (X=Y=H) gave 5-amino-2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine and 5-amino-4,6-dimethyl-2-hydroxypyrimidine, respectively.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer as nujol mulls.

2-Amino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine², 2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine³ and 4,6-dimethyl-2-hydroxypyrimidine⁴ were prepared by the methods described in literature and coupled with different aryl diazonium chlorides according to the method reported earlier¹. All the compounds were crystallized from DMF-ethanol mixture. The characteristics of compounds belonging to series I, II and III have been listed in Tables 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 2-AMINO-5-ARYLAZO-4-HYDROXY-6-METHYLPYRIMIDINES (I)

Sl. No.	X,Y	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis %	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	H	297 ^d	75	N, 30.57	30.24
2.	2-CH ₃	302	52	N, 28.80	28.64
3.	3-CH ₃	316 ^d	65	N, 28.80	28.68
4.	4-CH ₃	299	48	N, 28.80	28.39
5.	2-OCH ₃	307 ^d	63	N, 27.03	27.13
6.	3-OCH ₃	283	72	N, 27.03	26.92
7.	4-OCH ₃	298 ^d	70	N, 27.03	26.92
8.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	206	50	N, 25.64	25.50
9.	2-Cl	128	78	Cl, 13.47	13.28
10.	4-Cl	288	80	Cl, 13.47	13.26
11.	2-Br	266	76	Br, 26.00	26.10
12.	4-Br	245	74	Br, 26.00	25.90
13.	2-NO ₂	301	80	N, 30.56	30.49
14.	3-NO ₂	314 ^d	81	N, 30.56	30.46
15.	4-NO ₂	319 ^d	81	N, 30.56	27.23
16.	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	315	61	N, 27.23	27.23
17.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	299	65	Cl, 23.82	23.78

d = melts with decomposition.

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TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTICS OF 5-ARYLAZO-2,4-DIHYDROXY-6-METHYLPYRIMIDINES (II)

Sl. No.	X, Y	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis%	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	H	302-4	73	N, 24.35	24.67
2.	2-CH ₃	207-9	50	N, 22.95	22.85
3.	3-CH ₃	179 ^d	54	N, 22.95	22.91
4.	4-CH ₃	185 ^d	50	N, 22.95	23.07
5.	2-Cl	203-4	75	Cl, 13.42	13.49
6.	3-Cl	172	77	Cl, 13.42	13.28
7.	4-Cl	235 ^d	73	Cl, 13.42	13.44
8.	2-Br	205	78	Br, 25.89	26.10
9.	4-Br	220 ^t	75	Br, 25.89	24.92
10.	2-NO ₂	217-19	76	N, 25.45	25.40
11.	3-NO ₂	253	71	N, 25.45	25.53
12.	4-NO ₂	310	70	N, 25.25	25.58
13.	2,5-(Cl) ₂	303 ^d	63	Cl, 23.74	22.48
14.	2,5-(Br) ₂	300 ^d	65	Br, 41.24	41.09

^d—melts with decomposition.

TABLE 3—CHARACTERISTICS OF 5-ARYLAZO-4,6-DIMETHYL-2-HYDROXYPYRIMIDINES (III)

Sl. No.	X, Y	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis%	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	H	239	70	N, 24.57	24.63
2.	2-CH ₃	257 ^d	51	N, 23.14	23.28
3.	4-CH ₃	242	55	N, 23.14	22.98
4.	2-OCH ₃	255 ^d	48	N, 21.71	21.56
5.	4-OCH ₃	288	57	N, 21.71	21.77
6.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	318 ^d	55	N, 20.58	20.79
7.	2-Cl	230	65	Cl, 13.36	13.15
8.	3-Cl	210	72	Cl, 13.36	13.15
9.	4-Br	237	63	Br, 26.05	26.17
10.	2-NO ₂	298	70	N, 26.52	26.68
11.	3-NO ₂	304	78	N, 26.52	26.37
12.	4-NO ₂	303 ^d	69	N, 26.52	26.60
13.	2,5-(Br) ₂	308 ^d	77	Br, 41.45	41.80
14.	2,5-(Cl) ₂	284 ^d	79	Cl, 23.84	23.85

^d—melts with decomposition.

Method for reduction: A solution of I (X=Y=H) (2.29 g; 0.01 g mole) in acetic acid (20 ml) was added to a suspension of pure zinc (1.31 g; 0.02 g atom) in water (10-15 ml) slowly and with constant stirring. The mixture was first stirred at room temperature for 30-40 min and then heated on boiling water bath for 2-3 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered and the residue washed twice with water. Combined filtrate was neutralized with dilute NaHCO₃ and solid separated was crystallized from ethanol to give crystals, m.p. 285° (d), (yield 51%) which was identified as 2,5-diamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine [lit. m.p.⁶ 281-2° (d)]. (Found: N, 40.3. Calcd. for C₅H₈N₄O; N, 40.01%).

Similarly II (X=Y=H) and III (X=Y=H) were reduced and characterised by m.p. and elemental analysis.

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Search for New Hypoglycemic Agents.

Part—VII: Coumarinylsulphonyl Ureas,

Semicarbazides and Semicarbazones

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SULPHONYLUREAS^{1,2,3} have long been known in the therapy of diabetes. It has recently been reported that sulphonamido coumarins⁴ possess antidiabetic activity comparable to that of chlorpropamide. Moreover, some sulphonyl semicarbazides⁵ and semicarbazones have also exhibited marked hypoglycemic activity. Hence, the title compounds were prepared with a view to study their hypoglycemic efficacy.

4,5,7-Trimethylcoumarin on chlorosulphonation gave 4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl chloride, which on treatment with ammonia was converted to the corresponding sulphonamide. The latter was allowed to react with ethyl chloroformate in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ and dry acetone to yield ethyl N-(4,5,7-trimethyl-8-coumarinylsulphonyl) carbamate. The carbamate on condensation with various amines and hydrazines gave coumarinylsulphonyl ureas and coumarinylsulphonyl semicarbazides, respectively. Also, the treatment of the carbamate with hydrazine hydrate afforded a semicarbazide which was condensed with different aldehydes or ketones to furnish coumarinylsulphonyl semicarbazones.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The structures of compounds were confirmed by ir spectra and elemental analysis.